

**INVESTIGATION OF N-METHYL BACKBONE
ALTERATIONS IN HUMAN HISTONE 4 BY
CATALYSIS OF PCAF ENZYME**

IAKE804 – INDIVIDUAL STUDY ACTIVITY

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Abstract

Modifications can occur at different levels and time points during the biochemical process of gene expression, from DNA to the final peptide product. One of the most significant posttranslational modifications (PTMs) takes place in histone tails, which are special proteins that play a key role in the packaging and organisation of DNA, which means that can regulate indeed the state of chromatin, thereby influencing gene expression and regulation. This regulatory framework underlies the concept of *epigenetics*.

Among the diverse histone modifications, methylation and acetylation of amino acid residues have attracted significant attention in recent years. Most studies have focused on modifications of amino acid side chains due to their accessibility and well-characterized three-dimensional properties. However, modifications affecting the peptide backbone have emerged as an additional layer of regulation and are becoming increasingly relevant.

This study focuses on the enzyme PCAF (p300/CBP-associated factor), which is a specific histone lysine acetyltransferase (KAT) in charge of incorporating acetyl groups to the side chain of lysine residues. The aim of this project is to investigate whether the incorporation of a methyl group into the peptide backbone of human histone H4 (residues 1–16) influences the catalytic activity of PCAF, and whether this effect is dependent on the position of the modification within the histone sequence.

Keywords: acetylation; histone; lysine; epigenetics; peptide synthesis; posttranslational modifications; PCAF

Introduction

Posttranslational modifications (PTMs) of histones tails are key regulators of essential cell and biochemical processes, including gene expression, DNA repair and cell death or apoptosis. Among all these modifications, lysine acetylation is particularly widespread in nature. This enzymatic reaction is catalysed by histone lysine acetyltransferases (KAT), which is an enzyme that transfers an acetyl group from the abundant cellular metabolite acetyl coenzyme A (Acetyl-CoA) to the N ϵ -amino group of lysine residues on histone tails. Functionally, histone acetylation is associated with gene activation, as neutralization of the lysine's positive charge relaxes the compacted form (heterochromatin) of the chromatin into euchromatin, facilitating the action of transcriptional factors (TFs). [1]

Considering the biochemical context above mentioned, this Individual Study Activity (ISA) conducted during the Autumn semester 2025 within Jasmin Mecinovic's research group, has the primary aim of investigating the effect caused by the introduction of N-methyl amino acids in Human Histone 4 peptides (residues 1–16, $_{1}\text{SGRGKGGKGLGKGGAK}_{16}$). This study is focused on the systematic introduction of a single methyl group at each position at a time within the peptide sequence and characterizing how these chemical alterations influence biochemical properties of the histone tail by enzymatic assays. Moreover, the project aims to evaluate the impact of these modifications on the catalytic efficiency of histone lysine acetyltransferases (KATs), providing insight into the positional sensitivity of these enzymes and the broader implications of backbone methylation on histone-mediated regulation of gene expression.

By combining these approaches, the Individual Study Activity (ISA) seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of the interplay between histone chemical modifications and enzymatic activity, which is fundamental for interpreting epigenetic regulation in human cells.

Background

In eukaryotic cells, from yeast to humans, genomic DNA is packaged with a high level of complexity to form the structure known as chromatin. Despite this high level of organization and compaction, the genome remains dynamically accessible to the molecular machinery responsible for gene transcription, DNA replication, and damaged DNA repair, among others [2]. The fundamental repeating unit of chromatin is the nucleosome, which consists of around 145–147 base pairs (bp) of DNA wrapped around a histone octamer core (H2A, H2B, H3 and H4). Nucleosomes are linked by short stretches of DNA, commonly referred to as “*linker DNA*”, forming nucleosomal arrays that engage in short-range interactions with adjacent nucleosomes to generate chromatin fibres. Further interactions between these fibres contribute to the extensive compaction characteristic of condensed chromosomes (*Figure 1*).

The linear “*beads-on-a-string*” arrangement of nucleosomes constitutes the primary structure of chromatin. This primary structure serves as the first step for the formation of higher-order secondary and tertiary chromatin architectures.

Figure 1. Multiple levels of chromatin folding. [2]

Given the continually expanding repertoire of histone variants and post-translational modifications (PTMs) and considering that each nucleosome contains two

copies of each core histone, the number of theoretically possible chromatin primary structures is exponentially large. It is in this context where epigenetics plays a key role. Epigenetic regulation of gene expression (from the Greek *epi*, meaning “above” or “beyond”) is a dynamic process that enables genetically identical cells to acquire and maintain distinct patterns of gene expression, thereby establishing precise cellular identities and functions during development. This regulation is mediated by chemical modifications to the DNA itself, as well as to DNA-associated histone proteins, which together modulate chromatin structure and influence transcriptional outcomes. [3]

Beyond intrinsic nucleosomal variability, chromatin architecture is further shaped by architectural chromatin proteins (ACPs), nucleosome-binding proteins (including those that specifically recognize histone modifications) histone chaperones, and ATP-dependent chromatin remodellers, all of which influence chromatin organization at multiple scales. Structural changes to chromatin can occur at the nanoscale, such as the establishment of localized chromatin environments at active promoters, or at the microscale, where megabase-scale regions of the genome are organized into specialized domains. [4] Furthermore, chromatin can adopt two different states of compaction depending on the activation or suppression of gene expression. Heterochromatin is a tightly packed or condensed DNA state, whereas euchromatin is a more lightly packed DNA that promotes transcriptional activation (*Figure 2*).

Figure 2. Schematic diagram illustrating the organisational difference between Euchromatin and Heterochromatin. [5]

A defining feature of epigenetic regulation is the ability of epigenetic modifications to be stably maintained through cell division while remaining sufficiently dynamic to respond to developmental and environmental stimuli. This balance between stability and plasticity is mediated by three principal classes of epigenetic regulators: “*writers*”, which catalyse the deposition of epigenetic marks (including DNA and histone methyltransferases, histone acetyltransferases, and kinases); “*erasers*”, which remove these modifications (such as demethylases, histone deacetylases and phosphatases); and “*readers*”, which recognize and interpret epigenetic marks by binding to modified histones through specialized protein domains (*Figure 3*).**[6]**

Reader proteins facilitate the recruitment and assembly of appropriate transcriptional and chromatin-associated machineries at sites bearing specific epigenetic modifications. Consequently, histone modifications not only modulate chromatin accessibility by altering nucleosome structure and compaction but also serve as direct molecular signals that guide the localization of transcriptional regulators to defined genomic *loci*. **[6]**

Figure 3. Writers, readers and erasers of histone covalent modifications. Schematic representation of DNA (black filament) coiled around histone octamers. [6]

Histone lysine methyltransferases (KMTs) and acetyltransferases (KATs) are among the most well-established writer enzymes. Histone lysine methylation is catalysed by a diverse family of KMTs that utilize S-adenosylmethionine (SAM) as a methyl donor. These enzymes transfer a methyl group from SAM to the $N\epsilon$ atom of the lysine side chain through a conserved S_N2 reaction mechanism (*Figure 4*). The number of methyl groups installed on a given lysine residue is dictated by the structural and chemical properties of

the KMT active site, including substrate-binding geometry and product-release dynamics.

[7]

KMTs catalyse the transfer of one, two, or three methyl groups from SAM to the ϵ -amino group of lysine residues on histones and other proteins. During the reaction, SAM is converted into S-adenosylhomocysteine (SAH). Examples of KMT enzymes are G9a and SETD7. The reverse reaction is catalysed by a lysine demethylase enzyme (KDM).

Figure 4. Methylation reaction of the lysine side chain, catalysed by lysine methyl transferase (KAT). $FADH_2$ stands for Flavin Adenine Dinucleotide, in its reduced form (elaborated with ChemDraw)

KAT enzymes catalyse the transfer of an acetyl group from acetyl-CoA to the ϵ -amino group of lysine residues on histones (Figure 5). In this reaction, acetyl-CoA acts as the acetyl donor, linking cellular metabolic state to chromatin regulation, because intracellular acetyl-CoA levels directly influence histone acetylation and gene expression. PCAF and KAT8 are among other examples of KAT enzymes.

Figure 5. Acetylation reaction of the lysine side chain, catalysed by lysine acetyl transferase (KAT). Lysine deacetylases (KDACs) catalyse the reverse reaction (elaborated with ChemDraw).

Both methylation and acetylation of a lysine residue can be seen in the schematic reaction represented above in *Figure 4* and *Figure 5*. For these reactions to happen, the enzymes involved require the presence of adenosylmethionine (SAM) and acetyl-coenzyme A (acetyl-CoA), respectively. Researchers have historically focused on side-chain modifications of histones rather than backbone modifications primarily because side-chain modifications are more abundant, enzymatically regulated, and experimentally tractable, and because they fit naturally within established models of epigenetic regulation. [8]

Canonical H4 side-chain modifications (such as lysine acetylation and methylation) are catalysed by well-defined enzyme families (KATs, HDACs, KMTs, and demethylases), are reversible, and produce clear chemical changes that directly alter charge and protein–DNA interactions, making their functional consequences easier to detect and interpret. These modifications were readily identifiable using early biochemical and mass spectrometry (MS) techniques and could be directly linked to transcriptional activation or repression, nucleosome stability, and chromatin compaction, thereby forming the foundation of the “*histone code*” paradigm. [9]

In contrast, backbone modifications are comparatively rare, often subtle in their chemical signatures, and frequently lack clearly identified writer and eraser enzymes, which has made them more difficult to detect, manipulate, and integrate into mechanistic frameworks. Additionally, many backbone alterations were long regarded as damage or age-related chemical changes rather than regulated signals, further limiting early interest. [8] [9]

Of all the possibilities that can potentially lead to a backbone modification, some are depicted in *Figure 6*. Those are, for instance, cyclization, nitrogen and/or carbon substitutions, backbone extensions, or N-alkylation, which is the study-case concerning this project. [10]

Figure 6. Schematic representation of potential backbone modifications in peptide chains. [10]

Aim of the Individual Study Activity (ISA)

The main reason why this Individual Study Activity (ISA) represents and justifies a more than convenient and suitable option of scientific research is the high interest that backbone modifications have nowadays in relation to the ones taking place in the side chains of the amino acids.

Backbone modifications are particularly interesting and important in comparison to side-chain modifications because they alter the fundamental peptide framework that governs protein structure and dynamics, rather than modifying peripheral chemical groups. While side-chain modifications such as acetylation or methylation are typically reversible, enzyme-driven, and highly dynamic, backbone modifications can be long-lived or irreversible. By changing backbone geometry, flexibility and hydrogen-bonding capacity, these modifications can reshape histone tail conformation and nucleosome architecture in ways that side-chain modifications alone cannot achieve. What is more, backbone alterations can influence the accessibility, positioning, and recognition of canonical side-chain marks, effectively modulating how the histone code is interpreted. Structural level of regulation suggests that backbone modifications represent a deeper and more stable layer of chromatin control, complementing side-chain modifications and providing mechanistic explanations for sustained epigenetic memory and chromatin behaviours that are not fully explained by classical post-translational modifications.

Due to this determinative modification based on the introduction of a single methyl group bonded to the nitrogen atom of the peptide backbone, many hypotheses arise due to a possible steric clash or hindrance event that may occur with the resulting absence or loss of activity coming from the KAT enzyme. This idea constitutes the main question that needs to be answered in the current study. To investigate the role of the KAT catalysis, the peptide backbone underwent minimal alterations.

In this study, minimal modifications were introduced into the backbone of Human histone 4 (H4, 1-16) peptide by incorporating a methyl group on the nitrogen (-NH) of the peptide bond at each position in the sequence. This was achieved through systematic substitution of each amino acid with its N-methyl analogue. The ulterior enzymatic assays were carried out by using the enzyme PCAF (p300/CBP-associated factor) as histone acetyltransferase. Given the absence of a crystal structure for PCAF in complex with the H4 K8-acetylated peptide, we aimed to investigate the role of these small steric groups in each position of the sequence in the catalytic activity of PCAF.

The practical procedure is essentially based on the introduction of a methyl group (-CH₃) in each position of the aminoacidic sequence at a time, more particularly in the NH bond of the backbone, so the side chains are kept unmodified. By following this modification process, it is possible to determine what specific positions are crucial for the potential steric hindrance, and therefore a loss of activity, to occur, while PCAF has been proved to catalytically transfer an acetyl group to H4 K8.

Workflow

For these investigations, 16-mer H4 peptides (16 amino acid residues, ${}_{1}\text{SGRGKGGKGLGKGGAK}_{16}$) were selected, as this length provides an optimal balance for efficient enzymatic recognition and catalytic activity. In contrast, Histone 4 N-Methyl Arginine 17 (H4 NMeR17) was excluded from the sequence of study, enabling future studies on arginine-modifying enzymes such as peptidyl arginine deiminase 4 (PAD4) and protein arginine methyltransferase 1 (PRMT1).

At the outset, seventeen peptides (natural + 16 modified sequences) have been synthesised by following the Solid-Phase Peptide Synthesis technique (SPPS) protocol. In this synthesis, a single modification has been inserted in one position of each of them. That is, a single peptide presents a backbone N-methyl variation in one position at a time, modifying not only the molecular mass of the amino acid but also the position where the incorporated change is found within the peptide.

Using SPPS, we synthesized the natural H4 peptide along with N-methylated H4 peptides, systematically substituting each amino acid with its N-methyl analogue, resulting in a total of 16 unnatural peptides. It should be noted that synthesis and purification of the H4 NMeK16 peptide could not be accomplished due to time and stereochemical constraints during its synthesis and chain elongation.

As for the Fmoc-SPPS strategy (Fmoc stands for 9-Fluorenylmethyloxycarbonyl), Rink Amide MBHA resin (or abbreviated RAM resin) serves as physical support for the synthesis to begin with. This resin is initially Fmoc protected. The first step consists of a deprotection with a solution of piperidine (20%) in N,N-Dimethylformamide (DMF) for a time-lapse of 7 minutes. Right after this, the coupling step takes place enabled by HATU (CAS number: 148893-10-1) and N,N-Diisopropylethylamine (DIPEA, CAS number: 7087-68-5) dissolved in DMF at a temperature of approximately 75 °C for 13 minutes. The deprotection and coupling steps are repeated until the desired 16-mer H4 peptides were acquired. However, unnatural amino acids (N-Me building blocks) needed to be coupled manually. It is also significant to mention that the peptides obtained all have a C-terminal amide instead of a carboxylic acid because of the RAM resin used.

After obtaining the crude peptides, precipitated in solution thanks to the use of cold diethyl ether and centrifugation at 4°C / 5000 rpm for 5 minutes, the procedure proceeded by placing the new Falcon tubes under vacuum to dry again.

In the last step of the process, Fmoc deprotection with piperidine solution (20%) is needed, followed by a cleavage process with Trifluoroacetic acid (TFA, 95%), Triisopropylsilane (TIPS, 2.5%) and Milli-Q Water (2.5%) (dissolved together in a solution known as “*Cleavage cocktail*”), so the protecting groups of the side chains can be removed and the peptide can be detached from the resin. The mentioned process is schematically represented in *Figure 7*.

Figure 7. Schematic process of the key steps involved in the protocol used for Solid-Phase Peptide Synthesis (SPPS). (elaborated with ChemDraw).

As an additional step, assessment of the crude peptides was conducted by using the Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization – Time-of-Flight (MALDI-TOF) technique, with the aim of evaluating the expected mass and the purity of the sample for later purification with Reverse-Phase High-Performance Liquid-Chromatography (RP-HPLC), using as mobile phase of 7% acetonitrile (ACN), 0.1% TFA and Milli-Q Water. After purification, the pure peptides are placed in dry ice and are subjected to lyophilization. The expected pure peptide sequence without any modifications is displayed in *Figure 8*.

Figure 8. Amino acid sequence of histone 4 (only residues 1-16 are shown). Lysine 8 is highlighted (obtained from PepDraw).

In relation to the enzymatic assays, the pure peptides were dissolved in Milli-Q Water and their relative concentration was calculated by Nanodrop. A 4-(2-hydroxyethyl)-1-piperazineethanesulfonic acid (HEPES) zwitterionic buffer was used for the PCAF assays. The composition is as follows: HEPES 50 mM, ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) 0.1 mM and dithiothreitol (DTT) 1 mM. Each of the Eppendorf where the enzymatic assays are taking place contain buffer, the corresponding H4 peptide, PCAF and Acetyl-CoA, while the negative control lacks PCAF to ensure that acetylation is dependent on the enzyme. The reactant components are present in the following proportions: 10 μ M H4: 1 μ M PCAF: 30 μ M Ac-CoA. The reaction samples were shaken at 37 $^{\circ}$ C for 3 hours and potential conversion was monitored at two time-points, at 1-hour and 3-hour time, by MALDI-TOF MS.

Results and discussion

After carrying out enzymatic assessment with PCAF, the results are analysed and discussed. Upon initial observation, they show certain and apparent correlation that needs to be analysed with perspective.

The natural sequence of H4 (1-16) was effectively acetylated by PCAF as can be observed in *Figure 9*, reaching an approximate value of 85% after a reaction lapse of 3 hours, which may state the fact that PCAF is indeed active within its substrate in the studied sequence. Moreover, H4 NMeS1 (74%), H4 NMeG2 (80%) and H4 NMeR3 (85%) all show constants trends, indicating that PCAF can tolerate and carry on its reaction despite the N-Me substitution in these residues. On the other hand, for example,

H4 NMeG4 (67%), H4 NMeK5 (52%), H4 NMeG6 (27%) and H4 NMeG7 (34%) reveal a decreasing tendency in terms of acetylation in Lysine 8, leading to a null result when comes to H4 NMeK8 and H4 NMeG9 (both show 0% in duplication assays), most likely due to the presence of this methyl group in the proximity of the preferred substrate of PCAF.

Site-specific backbone amide N-methylated histone H4 peptides show increasing values of conversion into the acetylated form of the peptide, reaching up to approximately 92% in the cases of H4 NMeL10 and H4 NMeG11 after a time course of 3 hours. Interestingly, for H4 NMeL10, the PCAF activity seems to be restored because it reveals a high catalytic activity in the right next position after showing no activity in H4 NMeG9.

Figure 9. Results showing the acetylation (%) of natural histone 4 (H4) sequence and N-methylated (1-15) residues after 3 hours' time by enzyme PCAF (grey: no conversion observed; blue: lysine acetylated conversion). (Note: Standard Deviation, SD, for all the duplicates is represented within the bars except for NMeG14 & NMeA15).

For H4 NMeK12, H4 NMeG13, H4 NMeG14 and H4 NMeA15, the percentage of conversion indicates a clear regeneration with values ranging from 84%; 82%; 89% and 73%, respectively.

With the aim of confirming this trend, a time-dependent confirmation after 1 hour needed to be performed. In this occasion the experimental outcomes show a systematic and consistent increasing change in the conversion (%) consistent with the final reported values. As illustrated in Figure 10, positions 8 and 9 remain unaltered as no measurable response was observed (outcome was already null). The percentage of conversion is seen

to be increased considerably in the elapsed time between 1 hour and 3 hours for the rest of the altered sequences.

The tendency observed over the course of a 3-hour period can be confirmed after comparing with the period of 1 hour, at the onset of the first quenching reaction. If the results after 3 hours are observed more carefully, we can easily predict how these backbone modifications alter the capacity and ability of the enzyme to catalyse effectively the main substrate residue of the sequence, thus lysine 8 (labelled as NMeK8 in both *Figure 9* and *Figure 10*).

Figure 10. Results showing the acetylation (%) of natural histone 4 (H4) sequence and N-methylated (1-15) residues after 1 hour time by enzyme PCAF (grey: no conversion observed; blue: lysine acetylated conversion). (Note: Standard Deviation, SD, for all the duplicates is represented within the bars except for NMeG14 & NMeA15).

These incorporations of N-methyl groups into the amino acid backbone of the sequence could possibly constitute a geometrical restraint, a cluster collision or even a hindrance interference due to the lack of PCAF activity observed in the neighbouring amino acid residues (no activity is observed when lysine 8 and glycine 9 are backbone modified with a N-methyl group). PCAF activity appears reduced at these two positions, while increased activity is observed at the residues located at the far ends of the sequence, corresponding to the N- and C-terminal extremes. The enzymatic assays were carried out twice to provide consistency to the results obtained. Due to chemical complications, the synthesis of H4 NMeK16 had to be repeated twice, with the major difficulty eradicating

on the elongation from an unnatural amino acid as starter unit. In the end, this peptide was withdrawn from the study considering that further investigation will take place.

In summary, it can therefore be hypothesised that the insertion of a minimal change such as a small chemical group, in this case a methyl group in the backbone, can notably produce an impact on the effectiveness of PCAF depending on the position where this change has been incorporated in the target sequence of study.

Conclusion

Even though there is still a lack of structural information in terms of crystallographic accuracy, the utilisation of these unnatural N-methylated amino acid has demonstrated being a very useful tool for obtaining biochemical information regarding enzyme catalysis and its dynamics. Despite the significant biomedical relevance that KATs acquire nowadays, their total potential remains to be elucidated.

Although minor chemical variations were added within the backbone of the aminoacidic sequence, enzyme assays with PCAF showed that KAT-catalysed acetylation is observed to different degrees. The addition of a methyl group (-CH₃) attached to the nitrogen atom of the peptide bond of the lysine 8 (K8) is determinant to the reaction to occur or not as can be seen in the graph chart compared to the natural sequence where there is no methyl group involved.

It has been partially demonstrated that histone lysine acetyltransferases exhibit limited tolerance for minimal changes on the backbone of the lysine residue that undergoes acetylation reaction in the side chain. The data and results point that the presence of the backbone NH group of K8 and neighbouring amino acids is necessary for a productive KAT binding catalysis. It can be therefore hypothesized that the moiety NH participates in hydrogen bonding.

These results shed light on the intimate connection between N-methyl alterations in the backbone and other histone modifications in the regulation of the chromatin states. Overall, this work shed light on the molecular requirements for KAT catalysis, which are not only defined by the lysine's side chain subjected to the acetylation but also includes the relevant factor of an energetically favourable lysine backbone-KAT backbone interaction to properly align the residues in the catalytic pocket. That could be the case of

intramolecular hydrogen bonds, which may interfere within the three-dimensional structure of the histone and may be vital for the reaction to take place as some residues can interact with each other thanks to these dipole-dipole interactions. These findings demonstrate the importance of backbone in enzymatic catalysis.

Notwithstanding, there are still limitations of these enzymes' catalysis on substrates possessing backbone modifications, even in a small scale as a methyl group. Further investigations should undertake to gain additional insight into the KMTs way of action.

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Webography

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Appendix

A. Characterization of natural and modified peptides from Human Histone 4. (*Note: the N-methyl alterations within the chain are indicated in red.*)

Peptide	Sequence	Formula	m/z calc.
H4 (1-16) Natural	SGRGKGGKGLGKGGAK	C ₅₈ H ₁₀₈ N ₂₃ O ₁₈	1413.2
H4 (1-16) NMeS1	NMe SRGKGGKGLGKGGAK	C ₅₉ H ₁₁₀ N ₂₃ O ₁₈	1427.2
H4 (1-16) NMeG2	SNMe GRGKGGKGLGKGGAK	C ₅₉ H ₁₁₀ N ₂₃ O ₁₈	1427.3
H4 (1-16) NMeR3	SG NMe RGKGGKGLGKGGAK	C ₅₉ H ₁₁₀ N ₂₃ O ₁₈	1427.3
H4 (1-16) NMeG4	SGR NMe GKGGKGLGKGGAK	C ₅₉ H ₁₁₀ N ₂₃ O ₁₈	1427.8
H4 (1-16) NMeK5	SGRG NMe KGGKGLGKGGAK	C ₅₉ H ₁₁₀ N ₂₃ O ₁₈	1427.7
H4 (1-16) NMeG6	SGRGK NMe GKGLGKGGAK	C ₅₉ H ₁₁₀ N ₂₃ O ₁₈	1427.3
H4 (1-16) NMeG7	SGRGKG NMe GKGLGKGGAK	C ₅₉ H ₁₁₀ N ₂₃ O ₁₈	1427.3
H4 (1-16) NMeK8	SGRGKGG NMe KGLGKGGAK	C ₅₉ H ₁₁₀ N ₂₃ O ₁₈	1426.9
H4 (1-16) NMeG9	SGRGKGGK NMe GLGKGGAK	C ₅₉ H ₁₁₀ N ₂₃ O ₁₈	1427.3
H4 (1-16) NMeL10	SGRGKGGK NMe LGKGGAK	C ₅₉ H ₁₁₀ N ₂₃ O ₁₈	1428.2
H4 (1-16) NMeG11	SGRGKGGKGL NMe GKGGAK	C ₅₉ H ₁₁₀ N ₂₃ O ₁₈	1427.7
H4 (1-16) NMeK12	SGRGKGGKGL NMe KGGAK	C ₅₉ H ₁₁₀ N ₂₃ O ₁₈	1427.1
H4 (1-16) NMeG13	SGRGKGGKGLGK NMe GAK	C ₅₉ H ₁₁₀ N ₂₃ O ₁₈	1427.6
H4 (1-16) NMeG14	SGRGKGGKGLGKG NMe GAK	C ₅₉ H ₁₁₀ N ₂₃ O ₁₈	1427.8
H4 (1-16) NMeA15	SGRGKGGKGLGKGG NMe AK	C ₅₉ H ₁₁₀ N ₂₃ O ₁₈	1427.8
H4 (1-16) NMeK16	SGRGKGGKGLGKGGAN NMe K	C ₅₉ H ₁₁₀ N ₂₃ O ₁₈	-

B. MALDI-TOF MS assays for the characterization of the natural sequence and the SAM-mediated methylation of the modified peptides after purification (AP), human histone 4 (H4, 1-15). (*Note: Sodium and Potassium ions signals binding the peptides are represented with their respective chemical symbols, Na⁺ and K⁺, and showing a mass shift of +22 and +38, respectively. A +57 chemical shift can also be observed due to the addition of an extra glycine during the synthesis process.*)

Figure 11. H4 (1-16) Natural sequence (left) and H4 (1-16) NMeS1 (right).

Figure 12. H4 (1-16) NMeG2 (left) and H4 (1-16) NMeR3 (right).

Figure 13. H4 (1-16) NMeG4 (left) and H4 (1-16) NMeK5 (right).

Figure 14. H4 (1-16) NMeG6 (left) and H4 (1-16) NMeG7 (right).

Figure 15. H4 (1-16) NMeK8 (left) and H4 (1-16) NMeG9 (right).

Figure 16. H4 (1-16) NMeL10 (left) and H4 (1-16) NMeG11 (right).

Figure 17. H4 (1-16) NMeK12 (left) and H4 (1-16) NMeG13 (right).

Figure 18. H4 (1-16) NMeG14 (left) and H4 (1-16) NMeA15 (right).

C. Deconvoluted MALDI-TOF MS spectra resulting from the assays for SAM-methylation of the pure histone 4 natural sequence and N-methyl backbone modified peptides in the presence of PCAF after 1h (left) and 3h (right). Conditions for the assay: 10 μ M H4; 1 μ M PCAF; 30 μ M Acetyl-CoA. [Note: negative controls (NC) are provided on top of each spectrum to serve as a reference; m/z relative intensities of the Sodium and Potassium ionised peptides are shown as Na⁺ (+22) and K⁺ (+38), respectively. The chemical shift corresponding to the added acetyl group is indicated with an arrow (+42)].

Figure 19. Natural H4 sequence (1-15) after purification. Negative control at 1 h (top left) and 3 h (top right). Relative abundance of PCAF-mediated lysine 8 side-chain acetylation at 1 h (bottom left) and 3 h (bottom right).

Figure 20. Purified histone H4 peptide with site-specific backbone amide N-methylation at Ser1. Negative control at 1 h (top left) and 3 h (top right). Relative abundance of PCAF-mediated lysine 8 side-chain acetylation at 1 h (bottom left) and 3 h (bottom right).

Figure 21. Purified histone H4 peptide with site-specific backbone amide N-methylation at Gly2. Negative control at 1 h (top left) and 3 h (top right). Relative abundance of PCAF-mediated lysine 8 side-chain acetylation at 1 h (bottom left) and 3 h (bottom right).

Figure 22. Purified histone H4 peptide with site-specific backbone amide N-methylation at Arg3. Negative control at 1 h (top left) and 3 h (top right). Relative abundance of PCAF-mediated lysine 8 side-chain acetylation at 1 h (bottom left) and 3 h (bottom right).

Figure 23. Purified histone H4 peptide with site-specific backbone amide N-methylation at Gly4. Negative control at 1 h (top left) and 3 h (top right). Relative abundance of PCAF-mediated lysine 8 side-chain acetylation at 1 h (bottom left) and 3 h (bottom right).

Figure 24. Purified histone H4 peptide with site-specific backbone amide N-methylation at Lys5. Negative control at 1 h (top left) and 3 h (top right). Relative abundance of PCAF-mediated lysine 8 side-chain acetylation at 1 h (bottom left) and 3 h (bottom right).

Figure 25. Purified histone H4 peptide with site-specific backbone amide N-methylation at Gly6. Negative control at 1 h (top left) and 3 h (top right). Relative abundance of PCAF-mediated lysine 8 side-chain acetylation at 1 h (bottom left) and 3 h (bottom right).

Figure 26. Purified histone H4 peptide with site-specific backbone amide N-methylation at Gly7. Negative control at 1 h (top left) and 3 h (top right). Relative abundance of PCAF-mediated lysine 8 side-chain acetylation at 1 h (bottom left) and 3 h (bottom right).

Figure 27. Purified histone H4 peptide with site-specific backbone amide N-methylation at Lys8. Negative control at 1 h (top left) and 3 h (top right). Relative abundance of PCAF-mediated lysine 8 side-chain acetylation at 1 h (bottom left) and 3 h (bottom right).

Figure 28. Purified histone H4 peptide with site-specific backbone amide N-methylation at Gly9. Negative control at 1 h (top left) and 3 h (top right). Relative abundance of PCAF-mediated lysine 8 side-chain acetylation at 1 h (bottom left) and 3 h (bottom right).

Figure 29. Purified histone H4 peptide with site-specific backbone amide N-methylation at Leu10. Negative control at 1 h (top left) and 3 h (top right). Relative abundance of PCAF-mediated lysine 8 side-chain acetylation at 1 h (bottom left) and 3 h (bottom right).

Figure 30. Purified histone H4 peptide with site-specific backbone amide N-methylation at Gly11. Negative control at 1 h (top left) and 3 h (top right). Relative abundance of PCAF-mediated lysine 8 side-chain acetylation at 1 h (bottom left) and 3 h (bottom right).

Figure 31. Purified histone H4 peptide with site-specific backbone amide N-methylation at Lys12. Negative control at 1 h (top left) and 3 h (top right). Relative abundance of PCAF-mediated lysine 8 side-chain acetylation at 1 h (bottom left) and 3 h (bottom right).

Figure 32. Purified histone H4 peptide with site-specific backbone amide N-methylation at Gly13. Negative control at 1 h (top left) and 3 h (top right). Relative abundance of PCAF-mediated lysine 8 side-chain acetylation at 1 h (bottom left) and 3 h (bottom right).

Figure 33. Purified histone H4 peptide with site-specific backbone amide N-methylation at Gly14. Negative control at 1 h (top left) and 3 h (top right). Relative abundance of PCAF-mediated lysine 8 side-chain acetylation at 1 h (bottom left) and 3 h (bottom right).

Figure 34. Purified histone H4 peptide with site-specific backbone amide N-methylation at Ala15. Negative control at 1 h (top left) and 3 h (top right). Relative abundance of PCAF-mediated lysine 8 side-chain acetylation at 1 h (bottom left) and 3 h (bottom right).